

Multiscale modelling of Li-ion battery and battery-protective materials

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Background story and problem definition

Li-ion battery technology is expected to be the energy storage for choice for EVs in the coming years.

Advantages:

Better energy & power performance
Higher volume & weight efficiency

Disadvantages:

Battery life
Safety
Driving range
Charging time

Thermal runaway of Li-ion cells

Optimal range
15-35 °C

Below range:
Capacity drops
Slower charging
Reduce battery life

Above range:
Battery degradation
Prone to thermal runaway
Lower efficiency

External abusive conditions:
External heating
Over charging
Over discharging

Thermal runaway:
Smoke
Flames
Gas venting
Explosions

Mechanical abuse of Li-ion cells

State of art: Battery modelling

Thermal modelling:

Temperature discharge
Thermal runaway
Heat dissipation

+

Mechanical modelling:

Compression test
Mechanical integrity
Stress measurements

=

Thermo-mechanical coupled model:

Investigation of mechanical properties with controlled temperature changes

Thermo-mechanical model

Steady-state heat conduction

$$\nabla^T \mathbf{q} + Q = 0$$

$$\mathbf{q} = \begin{pmatrix} q_x \\ q_y \\ q_z \end{pmatrix} = - \begin{bmatrix} k_{xx} & k_{xy} & k_{xz} \\ k_{yx} & k_{yy} & k_{yz} \\ k_{zx} & k_{zy} & k_{zz} \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \end{pmatrix} = -k \nabla T$$

$$\nabla T = \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x}, \frac{\partial}{\partial y}, \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \right]$$

$$-\nabla^T (k \nabla T) + Q = 0$$

Heat dissipated by convection and radiation is ignored here!

Transient heat conduction

$$c \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} - \nabla^T (k \nabla T) + Q = 0$$

Thermoelastic effect:

$$\sigma_{ij} = C_{ijkl} \epsilon_{kl}^M = C_{ijkl} (\epsilon_{kl} - \epsilon_{kl}^T)$$

$$\epsilon_{kl}^T = \alpha \Delta T \delta_{kl}$$

$$\delta_{kl} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } k = l \\ 0 & \text{if } k \neq l \end{cases}$$

$$\sigma_{ij} = C_{ijkl} (\epsilon_{kl} - \alpha \Delta T \delta_{kl})$$

Project aim and overall framework

Battery pack enclosure: load bearing + heat dissipation

Composite material will 'wrap' cells to protect them from mechanical and thermal abuses, and facilitate the load transfer in case of collisions

Composite structure can have different designs (porous, coolant filled, lattice structure)

Porous foam

Coolant filled

Lattice structures

Overall framework

- Multiscale characterisation and modelling
- Thermal-mechanical multiphysics modelling

Battery cell

Multifunctional porous casing
(Thermal management & Energy absorbing)

Experimental unit composed of Li-ion cell + protective encasing

Microscale modelling

Microscale modelling

Issues with last model:

- Perfect-bond between layers
- Bad meshing in thinnest layers

Improvements in latest model:

- Layers are bonded using 3 different approaches
- Fine meshing in thin elements
- Closest results obtained by partition and cohesive models

Thermal properties via numerical methods

- Temperature profile obtained from numerical simulation
- Temperature profile obtained from PDE heat equation, with same BCs (100°C)
- Both data compared by PDE code, fitting the thermal diffusivity value

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \alpha \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2}$$

- Investigation at different range of **volume fraction** V_f

	Size (μm)
<i>L</i>	450
<i>D</i>	160
<i>l</i>	30 - 40
<i>d</i>	10 - 20

Mesoscale modelling

Constitutive model

- **Homogenization** of the jellyroll by **rule of mixtures**.

$$E_c = fE_f + (1 - f)E_m$$

- **Johnson-Cook plasticity** is used for model the yielding behaviour of the **jellyroll** (composite material).

$$\sigma^0 = [A + B(\epsilon^{-pl})^n](1 - \hat{\theta}^m)$$

- **Von-Mises plasticity** model was utilised to predict the plastic behaviour of the **metallic shell and winding nail**.

$$\sigma_v = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}[(\sigma_1 - \sigma_2)^2 + (\sigma_2 - \sigma_3)^2 + (\sigma_3 - \sigma_1)^2]}$$

Material properties

Component	Material	Plasticity model
Winding nail	Stainless steel	Isotropic, Johnson-Cook
Shell	Stainless steel	Isotropic, Johnson-Cook
Jellyroll	NCO electrode	Isotropic, Johnson-Cook

Mesoscale mechanical model

Homogenized model:

- Rule of Mixtures for mechanical properties
- Material properties obtained from literature review [4]
- Compressive test cell data obtained from [5]
- Very good agreement

Macroscale modelling

Macroscale thermal analysis on battery pack

- Simulation of an overheated cell inside a battery pack.
- Investigation of heat propagation and thermal conductivity importance of matrix.

Thank you for listening

Queen Mary

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